

A Hitherto Unknown Tibetan Religious Chronicle: from Probably the Early Fourteenth Century

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Abstract: The recent publication in Lhasa of a number of *Dbu' / Sba bzhed* texts contains a work that has been misidentified as belonging to the *Dbu' / Sba bzhed* corpus. In fact, it is a short chronicle of Buddhism (*chos 'byung*) that, to my knowledge, was not published before. The "chronology of the Teaching" (*bstan rtsis*) that forms its coda allows us tentatively to date it to the early fourteenth century. The last folio of the manuscript appears to be damaged, but the concluding words apparently mention *Dbus pa Blo gsal Rtsod pa'i seng ge* by name. He was himself the author of a chronicle, a manuscript copy of which has so far not been located. Aside from simply "being there," the value of the present chronicle consists in the main of the many citations of earlier writings on aspects of Tibetan history.

Key words: history, *chos 'byung*, *Dbus pa Blo gsal*, Tibetan Chronology

To repeat the obvious and risking tedium, it is trivially true that manuscripts are liable to become undone and even incomplete. The sequence of the folios can easily get mixed up or, what is worse, individual folios can get lost along the way, particularly when the manuscripts to which they belong circulate in an unbound form, as they often do, or when they are being read or when, lying on a table or chair, they are about to be read. Irrespective of whether the individual is reading a manuscript in a reasonably well appointed residence of *Snar thang* monastery, in a meditation cave somewhere in the remote reaches of *Lho brag*, in a suburban Parisian apartment, or in a home in Lancaster, Massachusetts, it takes but a careless movement of the arm to bring its folios into disarray. Folios may get mixed up or even "lost" while reading. If the reader is drinking something, then an unthinking hand may cause his drink to spill on the folio he is reading or, worse, on the entire manuscript, leading him or her to place it or the drenched folios elsewhere to dry. An unanticipated gust of wind from an open window or door may blow the folios asunder; a folio can then inadvertently slip under a piece of furniture and be forgotten. Countless are indeed the ways in which a manuscript can become undone and

thus incomplete, let alone damaged. Careless storage also frequently contributes to this, as anyone will readily realize when he has seen how manuscripts were kept in the virtual floor-to-ceiling "library" of Se ra monastery's Byes seminary and what the "Cultural Revolution" had left of the library of Zhwa lu monastery. I recently saw, as I had done earlier, hundreds of manuscripts that were roughly piled up against one another in the Byes seminary and, I remember how, in the early eighties, I beheld in unbelieving astonishment an enormous pile of loose folios from I do not know how many manuscripts that had been "stored" on the floor of one of Zhwa lu's antechambers since the "Cultural Revolution" — I also do not know whether they were sorted and properly stored in the meantime. I also recall a private showing in Lhasa, again in the early eighties, of video footage a Sino-Japanese television team had recently shot in Gu ge, in West Tibet, that literally showed thousands of folios from untold numbers of manuscripts that laid strewn across the landscape as far as the video recorder's lens was able to see. This was a horrendous cultural catastrophe! However, truth be told as I write these lines, there are also a good number of caves in northern Nepal and in Mnga' ris where one can find even today abandoned piles of loose folios from one does not know how many manuscripts. Who knows what treasures these caves may contain!

More often than not, it is the title-folio and the last folio[s] of a manuscript that first go astray. A not uncommon remedy in the case of the former is that a later reader simply affixes a "new" title page to the rest of the manuscript or guesses sometimes correctly and sometimes incorrectly of what the manuscript is a witness of or, indeed, what it may be about. A case in point is the affixation of a generic title, in this instance *Bod snga rabs pa tshad ma'i spyi don*, roughly, *A Study of Logic and Epistemology of an Early Tibetan Generation*, to a manuscript of a study by Dar ma dkon mchog (ca. 1180—ca. 1240) of Phu thang in Dbus-he is also known as Dharmaratna—for which the title page had gone missing.^① Text-internal evidence indicates that the actual title of this work which is concerned with explicating some of the more knotty points in Dharmakīrti's (7th c.) celebrated *Pramāṇaviniścaya* was in fact *Rtlog ge rigs pa'i rgyan gyi snying po*. Not much was needed to come up with this not irrelevant datum. All that was required was to read the final page of this manuscript, for it is always the case that the title of the text, and usually the name of the author and other data surrounding its composition are given in the colophon of the manuscript, that is, in its final page or final pages.

A recent instance of where a manuscript evidently had no "title" page and where its final folio was so tattered as to be virtually illegible with the result that that the nature of

① The manuscript written in a cursive *dbu med* script consists of ninety-seven numbered folios, whereby fol. 64 occurs twice, one as simply "64" and once as "64 lower ('og ma)." It was part of the Tibetan collection of the Nationalities Library of the Cultural Palace of Nationalities [Minzu wenhua gong], Beijing, and was cataloged under no. 004783 (1).

this manuscript was incorrectly guessed at, is found in a recently published collection of texts that purport to be witnesses of a work that may have been titled *Dbā'—, Sba—, or Rba bzhed*. In this short paper, I hope, well, to piece together bits of evidence for holding that a manuscript to which the editor of this publication had given the title *Rba bzhed* is in fact a work that belongs to the genre of "religious chronicle" (*chos 'byung*), that it has actually *nothing* to do with the other works of the collection that he edited, and that, what is more, may very well have been written in the first decades of the fourteenth century.

The last few years witnessed the publication of two collections of computer generated texts that were designated *Dbā'—or Sba—or Rba bzhed*—I will refer to these as the *Dbā' bzhed* corpus. The original title of these texts is not known, even if a consensus is slowly solidifying into the idea that it was *Dbā' bzhed*, the *Ur—*text of which would date from around 800 A. D. The first collection was compiled and [allegedly] edited by a certain Bde skyid,^① the second was edited and published by Longs khang Phun tshogs rdo rje. Reading through the latter, it is evident that Phun tshogs rdo rje was generally in possession of better editorial skills than Bde skyid. Similar to Bde skyid's collection in terms of scope, Phun tshogs rdo rje's volume contains editions of the following texts:^② [*Sangs rgyas kyi chos bod kham su ji ltar byung ba'i bka' mchid kyi yi ge*] *dbā'i bzhed* [pp. 1–48], *Zas gtad kyi lo rgyus* [pp. 49–58],^③ *Sba bzhed* [pp. 59–157], *Bka' tshigs kyi yi ge zhib mo la zhabs btags pa* [pp. 158–258], *Rba bzhed* [pp. 259–318]. The volume's somewhat irregular table of contents [pp. 1–2] and the reproduced texts are preceded by Phun tshogs rdo rje's general remarks on these works in his clarification of the published manuscripts (*dpe skrun gsal bshad*) [pp. 1–9] and a short biography of *Dbā' Gsal snang* [pp. 1–4]. In the first, he discusses the relative merits of the designations of the first four works, examines the question of their authorship, gives an analysis of what the which is titled *Zas gtad kyi lo rgyus*, "Annals of the Funerary Food Offering Ritual," and informs us that all the manuscripts that are reproduced in this volume were borrowed from Pa tshab Pa sangs dbang 'dus. He makes no mention of the last of these, namely

① See <*Rba bzhed*> *phyogs bsgrigs*, ed. Bde skyid (Beijing: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2009). This collection is briefly discussed in my "A Note on the Diffusion of the Translations of the Large *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra* (*Yum rgyas pa*) in Early Tibet," which is currently under preparation. For further remarks on this corpus, see also notes 43–44 of my "Some Remarks on the Textual Transmission and Text of Bu ston Rin chen grub's *Chos 'byung*, His Chronicle of Buddhism in India and Tibet," which is forthcoming in the *Revue d'études Tibétaines*.

② *Dbā' bzhed*, ed. Longs khang Phun tshogs rdo rje, Gangs can rig mdzod 56 (Lhasa: Bod ljongs bod yig dpe rnying dpe skun khang, 2010); something has gone awry with its table of contents.

③ The first two were translated and published in facsimile in *Dbā' bzhed. The Royal Narrative Concerning the Bringing of the Buddha's Doctrine in Tibet*, tr. Pasang Wangdu and H. Diemberger, Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-Historische Klasse, Denkschriften, 291. Band / Tibetan Academy of Social Sciences of the Autonomous Region Tibet (Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 2000), 23–91, 91–105.

what he has designated *Rba bzhed*. Finally, while useful, his biographical sketch of *Dbā' Gsal snang* does not supersede the details 'Brong bu Tshe ring rdo rje had given anent the family in an earlier paper.^① Sandwiched between these is an essay by Pa sangs dbang 'dus himself [pp. 1–14] in which this well-known scholar discusses the relative merits of the texts. His essay is essentially a replay of the *Introduction* of his earlier co-authored English translation of the *Dbā' bzhed*.^②

The last tract in this collection, pp. 259–317, purportedly a reproduction of a manuscript of the *Rba bzhed*, merits some attention, in that it concerns the reproduction of a manuscript that is actually radically different from any one of the *Dbā'/Sba bzhed* manuscripts that were published so far. In fact, it shares next to nothing with the other texts that Phun tshogs rdo rje included in his volume. And what should have alerted him that something was amiss with his identification, let alone inclusion in this volume, is that: [a] the title *Rba* [or *Dbā'* or *Sba*] *bzhed* appears nowhere in the text, [b] that the text in numerous places indicates influences and even citations from authors who postdate the imperial period (ca. 630–841) by almost five hundred years, [c] that it contains a listing of the names of important translators in rough chronological order, and [d] that it ends with an essay on Buddhist chronology (*bstan rtsis*). Indeed, the text itself is divided into six chapters (*skabs*) and a long afterword that are *in toto* distributed over three General Sections (*spyi don*); these are:

[1] Identifying the holy religion (*dam pa'i chos ngos bzung ba*) [pp. 259–274]

[2] Explaining the succession of kings (*rgyal po'i rabs bshad pa*) [pp. 275–280]

[3] Explaining aspects of monasteries and translations of the holy religion during the early spread of the Teaching (*bstan pa snga dar gyi dus su gtsug lag khang dang dam pa'i chos bsgyur ba'i skor bshad pa*) [pp. 281–292]

[4] Explaining aspects of the way in which the Buddha's Teaching developed from Kham (*sangs rgyas kyi bstan pa mdo* ['] *kham nas 'phel ba'i skor bshad pa*) [pp. 293–297]

[5] Explaining aspects of the way in which the Buddhist communities developed in Dbus and Gtsang (*sangs rgyas kyi sde pa dbus gtsang du' phel ba'i skor bshad pa*) [pp. 297–308]

[6] Explaining the later spread of the Teaching (*bstan pa phyi dar bshad pa*) [pp. 308–312]

① See his "Dbā' gsal snang gi me che'i lo rgyus skor gyi dpyad brjed," *Krung go'i bod rig pa* 2 (2005), 37–48.

② *Dbā' bzhed. The Royal Narrative Concerning the Bringing of the Buddha's Doctrine in Tibet*, tr. Pasang Wangdu and H. Diemberger, 1–14.

[Afterword,]

[A] Explaining the duration of the Teaching in general (*spyir bstan pa'i tshad bshad pa*) [pp. 313–314]

[B] Explaining the duration of the Teaching in particular (*bye brag tu bstan pa'i tshad bshad pa*) [pp. 314–318]

The General Sections begin with the second chapter where we read Second General Section (*spyi don 2 pa*) at the outset—the first chapter does not have anything that might be the equivalent of “First General Section” (**spyi don 1*)! The Second General Section covers chapters two–six. The third and last General Section (*spyi don 3 pa*) consists of what I have called “Afterword.” Given the above outline, it should be immediately obvious, and not necessarily only to one with an intimate knowledge of Tibetan literature, that this manuscript has absolutely nothing to do with any of the *Dbā' bzhed* or *Sba bzhed* [*zhabs btags ma*] or *Rba bzhed* manuscripts that have been published so far. Further, it is evident from the outline of the contents of this manuscript that I have given above, that it is structurally and in terms of its content far closer to such famous religious chronicles as the ones by, for example, Nyang ral Nyi ma'i 'od zer (1124–92) of circa 1190, Mkhas pa Lde'u of the 1260s, and Bu ston Rin chen grub (1290–1364) of 1322–6. Indeed, upon closer inspection, one must come to the conclusion that it is in fact a religious chronicle and that it therefore belongs to the *chos 'byung* genre!

The entire published cognate manuscripts/texts published of the *Dbā' bzhed* corpus, only the so-called *Sba bzhed zhabs btags ma*, the “*Sba bzhed* to which is added an appendix,” cites one other Tibetan work in its narrative, namely, Bu ston's religious chronicle.^① It is quite different with this work, for the unknown author makes a substantial number of specific references to authors or quotations from a good number of Tibetan sources. These include Rtsang [also: Gtsang] nag pa [pp. 271, 294, 296] — I identify him as Gtsang nag pa Brtson 'grus seng ge (? — after 1195), who is known to have written a religious chronicle—and Bcom ldan ral gri (1227–1305) [pp. 276, 290, 315], which is the alias of Dar ma rgyal mtshan.^② In addition, he also cites Khu [? ston Brtson-'grus-g. yung-drung's (1011–1075)] *Lo rgyus chen mo* [pp. 277, 283], which may be the same as the *Khu'i yig* [pp. 285, 286], a *Dbā' bzhed* [p. 284], and a *Bla bzhed*

① See *Une chronique ancienne de Bsam yas, Sba bzhed*, ed. R. A. Stein (Paris: Publications de l'Institut des Hautes Études, 1961), 54, and *Bashi*, ed. and tr. Tong Jinhua and Huang Bufan (Chengdu: Si khron mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 1990), 160. That Bu ston is cited in this work seems to have been first noticed in F. Faber, “The Council of Tibet According to the *Sba bzhed*,” *Acta Orientalia* XLVII (1986), 39–40.

② For some remarks concerning Dar ma rgyal mtshan, see my “A Treatise on Buddhist Epistemology and Logic Attributed to Klong chen Rab 'byams pa (1308–64) and Its Place in Indo-Tibetan Intellectual History,” *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 31 (2003), 406 ff., and also K. R. Schaeffer and L. W. J. van der Kuip, *An Early Tibetan Survey of Buddhist Literature. The Bstan pa rgyas pa rgyan gyi nyi 'od of Bcom ldan ral gri*, Harvard Oriental Series, vol. 64 (Cambridge: The Department of Sanskrit and Indian Studies, Harvard University, 2009), 3–8.

[pp. 285, 287]. Finally, in part B of the *Afterword*, he privileges the calculations done by Dar ma rgyal mtshan, and then mentions those by Slob dpon Bsod nams rtse mo (1142–82), Sa skya Paṇḍita Kun dga' rgyal mtshan (1182–1251), Śākyaśrībhadrā (1127–1225), Bla ma Chos kyi rgyal po, that is, 'Phags pa Blo gros rgyal mtshan (1235–1280), and Dbus pa Blo gsal.^① To be noted is that the first and the last are scholars associated with Snar thang monastery and the Bka' gdams pa school, whereas the second, third and fifth are members of the same family that ruled over Sa skya monastery and thus were exponents of the Sa skya pa school. It therefore stands to reason that the author's doctrinal-spiritual loyalties resided in one of these two schools or, perhaps less likely, in both. I would be inclined to put my money on him belonging to the Bka' gdams pa.

The way in which the author referred to Bcom ldan ral gri either suggests that there existed a personal bond between them and that he was his disciple, that he greatly admired him, or both, for he mentions him in a very respectful manner as “lord among scholars” (*mkhas pa'i dbang phyug*) and suitably employs the honorific forms for “do, write” (*mdzad*) and “aver, maintain” (*bzhed*). The first reference points to the fact that Bcom ldan ral gri had held that a certain Rupati was a contemporary of the legendary Tibetan ruler Gnya' khri btsan po and the second simply informs the reader that he or she should consult his *Bstan pa rgyas pa rgyan gyi nyi 'od*, that is, his title catalog of translated scripture for the contents of the early ninth century *Ldan dkar ma* and *'Phang thang ma* catalogs.^② The source for the first reference is not as clear-cut. True, the *Bstan pa rgyas pa rgyan gyi nyi 'od* does mention Rupati in the context of the word “Tibet [an]” (*bod*), but absent from it is his alleged contemporaneity with Gnya' khri btsan po.^③ The same absence is also met with in Bcom ldan ral gri's chronicle on which see below. The third and last mention of Bcom ldan ral gri occurs in part B of the *Afterword* where the author is concerned with enumerating some six different attempts at fixing the year of the Buddha's nirvana, the A [nno] N [irvanae] or AN, that is, his passing, without giving any specific indications about the one with which he would be inclined to side. It is hardly an accident, I submit, that he would begin his enumeration of the results of several different *bstan rtsis*-chronologies with Bcom ldan ral gri's calculation;

dus 'khor gyi lugs kyis ston pa 'das nas bya'i lo phan chad lo nyis stong dang

① For these and other calculations, see D. Seyfort Rugg, “Notes on some Indian and Tibetan reckonings of the Buddha's Nirvāṇa and the Duration of his Teaching,” *The Dating of the Historical Buddha / Die Datierung des historischen Buddha*, Part 2 (Symposien zur Buddhismusforschung, IV, 2), ed. H. Bechert (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1992), 263–90.

② For the second point, see Schaeffer and van der Kuijp, *An Early Tibetan Survey of Buddhist Literature. The Bstan pa rgyas pa rgyan gyi nyi 'od of Bcom ldan ral gri*, 115–193.

③ Schaeffer and van der Kuijp, *An Early Tibetan Survey of Buddhist Literature. The Bstan pa rgyas pa rgyan gyi nyi 'od of Bcom ldan ral gri*, 105.

dgu bcu rtsa 3 song bar mkhas pa'i dbang phyug bcom ldan ral gri bzhed ...

The lord of scholars Bcom ldan ral gri averred, that according to the *Kālacakra's* position, up to the hen-year (1261), 2093 years have elapsed since the passing of the Buddha, ...

So far, I have only come across one passage from Bcom ldan ral gri's writings to which I have access that has anything to say about chronology. This is his short religious chronicle of 1261, where we read the following^①:

de la dus 'khor gyi lugs kyis sangs rgyas 'das nas lo nyis stong dang dgu bcu rtsa gsum song ste / ting nge 'dzin gyi dus la dgu bcu rtsa lnga song ngo // nyis stong dang brgya phrag dgu dang lo bdun du gnas te lcags mo bya'i lo brtsis so // sing ga gling pa'i lugs kyis stong brgyad brgya dang lo bzhi song ngo //

In that connection, according to the *Kālacakra's* position, 2093 years have elapsed since the passing of the Buddha; in terms of [the fifth five hundred-year period of] spiritual integration, 93 years have passed. [His teaching] will remain for 2937 years; calculated in the iron-female-hen year (1261).^② According to the Sinhalese position, 1804 years have passed.

Beginning with the year 1261 and with the aid of the *Kālacakra*, he thus calculated the Buddha's passing to have occurred in *circa* 832 BCE. There is no question that this calculation places him among the very first Tibetan scholars to make express use of the

① *Bstan pa rgyan gyi me tog, dbu med* manuscript in 28 folios, Cultural Palace of Nationalities, catalog no. 007916 (10), 26b [= *Thub pa'i bstan pa rgyan gyi me tog, dbu med* manuscript in 31 folios, Cultural Palace of Nationalities, catalog no. 007114, 30a, = *Thub pa'i bstan pa rgyan gyi me tog, dbu med* manuscript in 24 folios, Nepal German Manuscript Preservation Project Reel L493/2, 23b]. Their minor variant readings are immaterial. Dga' ldan khri pa XIV Rin chen'od zer (1453—1540) mentions a work by Dar ma rgyal mtshan titled *Bstan rtsis thub bstan rgyan gyi me tog*; see the *Bstan rtsis gsal ba'i sgrom me, dbu med* manuscript in 145 folios, Cultural Palace of Nationalities, catalog no. 002324 (1), 23b. It is possible that this is a separate work on the subject of Buddhist chronology.

② Mkhas pa Lde'u, *Mkhas pa lde'us mdzad pa'i rgya bod kyi chos'byung*, ed. Chab spel Tsho brtan phun tshogs and Nor brang O rgyan, *Gangs can rig mdzod 3* (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1987), 409, follows his remark anent possibly the year 1146 CE with a reproduction of the chronological calculation that Śākyaśribhadra had carried out in 1207 while he was at Thang po che monastery. Mkhas pa Lde'u then notes that 385 years of the *mgon pa'i dus*, that is, the *abhidharma*-period, had elapsed in an iron-female-hen year. The *abhidharma*-period begins at 3000 AN, so that this year represents 3385 AN. This means that, following the Bka' gdams pa chronology, the year in question is *circa* 1249, that is, the earth-female-hen year. It is not at all impossible that Mkhas pa Lde'u's original text simply had a twelve-year duodenary notation, that is, a hen-year, which was then later recalibrated into a sixty-year sexagenary notation, hence the potential slippage of a one twelve-year cycle.

Kālacakra for ascertaining the duration (*gnas tshad*) of Buddhism and, by implication, the AN. What is more, while we do not know how he arrived at his result, it does come rather close to the calculations attributed to Dol po pa and others, who opted for *circa* 832 BCE.^① The so-called Sinhalese position points to the Buddha's passing in 544 BCE, for this is precisely the year that is obtained when 1804 is subtracted from the current year 1261, and the year 544 BCE is exactly the position that was also maintained by *Ākyasribhadra* who is quoted a few lines below.^② The author deals with the latter in an almost perfunctory manner, as he does the two Sa skya pa scholars, Slob dpon Bsod nams rtse mo and Sa skya Paṇḍita, whom he mentions immediately following Bcom ldan ral gri; he writes:

*me mo phag [g]i lo rin po che bsod nams rtse mos na la rtse gnas po che'i gtsug
lag khang du brtsis te lo sum stong sum brgya song zhing / me pho byi ba'i lo
rje btsun chen po 'das pa'i chos grwa btsugs pa'i dus su sa skya paṇḍi ta chen
pos brtsis te lo sum stong sum brgya 49 song bar bzhed /*

The fire-female-pig year (1167): Rin po che Bsod nams rtse mo performed a calculation at the monastery of Na la rtse gnas po che and three thousand three hundred had expired, and the fire-male-rat year (1216); Sa skya Paṇḍita performed a calculation at the time of conducting a convocation [read: *chos 'khor*] on the occasion of Rje btsun chen po Grags pa rgyal mtshan's (1147—1216) passing and averred that three thousand three hundred and 49 years had expired since the Buddha's nirvana.

The relevant sources for these two calculations of the Buddha's nirvana that allegedly took place on the chronologically awkward year of *circa* 2133 BCE (!) will be noted below. Suffice it to mention here that the author uses the honorific *bzhed* rather than *'dod*, and I do not think this is without importance.

The possibility of the author having written this work towards the end of the first half of the fourteenth century is further in evidence by the fact that Nyi ma rgyal mtshan dpal bzang po (ca. 1260—ca. 1330) is the last one he has registered in the list of major Tibetan Sanskritists [p. 312] who were active in translating Sanskrit texts into Tibetan. He is also the only one in this list who is styled "Lama-translator" (*bla ma lo tsā ba*). To be sure,

① See Seyfort Rugg, "Notes on some Indian and Tibetan Reckonings of the Buddha's Nirvāṇa and the Duration of his Teaching," 277—8.

② See, respectively, H. Bechert, "The Origin and the Spread of the Theravāda Chronology," *The Dating of the Historical Buddha / Die Datierung des historischen Buddha*, Part 2 (Symposien zur Buddhismusforschung, IV, 2), ed. H. Bechert (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1992), 329—43, and Seyfort Rugg, "Notes on some Indian and Tibetan Reckonings of the Buddha's Nirvāṇa and the Duration of his Teaching," 266.

one could argue that 'Phags pa may have been one of his main teachers, since he styles him Bla ma Chos kyi rgyal po. The epithet "Religious King" (**dharmarāja*) that he uses for 'Phags pa implies an awareness that 'Phags pa was invested with both religious and political competence, and this may be the sole reason why he is so styled. On the other hand, like many, he may have heard one or the other teaching from him and this would explain the "Lama" part. As far as his use of "Lama-translator" for Thar pa gling Lo tsā ba is concerned, it probably indicates that, as is the case with Bu ston and a host of others, who also refer to him in this manner, the anonymous author stood in a disciple-teacher relationship with this important scholar who is reputed to have been abbot of Bodhgayā for three years.^① Hence, while not airtight, the evidence does strongly suggest that Nyi ma rgyal mtshan dpal bzang po's *floruit* is this work's *terminus a quo*. The three translators the author mentions immediately preceding to him are:

1. Shong ston Rdo rje rgyal mtshan (late 13th c.)
2. Shong Lo tsā ba Blo gros brtan pa (late 13th c.)
3. Lo tsā ba [Yar lung pa] Grags pa rgyal mtshan (1242–? 1346)^②

Of undoubted significance is of course that the names of such translator-Sanskritists as the great and enormously influential Dpang Lo tsā ba Blo gros brtan pa (1276–1342) and Bu ston are not found in this list.

It is important to note that Phun tshogs rdo rje indicates that even though this work's final page was tattered and in many parts illegible, he was still able to discern the name "Dbus pa Blo gsal" (*mjug byang shog ldebs gcig 'dug pa las "dbus pa blo gsal" zhes pā tsam las yi ge gzhan rnam ches mi gsal bas rang sor bzhag*). Of course, *dbus pa blo gsal*, "the bright one from Dbus," is a nickname and an epithet, and thus by no means a recognized Tibetan name in religion. This is not as insignificant as it might appear, because there is quite a bit of uncertainty about his actual name in religion, not to mention his dates. Indeed, later sources, suggest two individuals who are called Dbus pa Blo gsal, but whose names in religion were "Byang chub ye shes" and "Sangs rgyas 'burn." Another nickname under which he is known is Rtsod pa'i seng ge, which means "Lion of Debate."

① A biographical sketch of this man, who is also known as Thar pa gling Lo tsā ba, is found in Bya btang pa Padma rdo rje, *Dpyal gyi gdung rabs xa ra tshags dang gang gā'i chu rgyun gnyis gcig tu bris pa-kun gsal me long*, ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 2008), 73–5. Bya btang pa completed his work, one that was based on several earlier studies that chronicle the history of the Dpyal family, in 1546 at Thar pa gling monastery. Thar pa gling was one of the Dpyal family's "private" monasteries and he compiled his work in part at the behest of a young scion of this family, Ngag dbang grags pa lhun grub rgyal mtshan dpal bzang po (1530–?).

② For this man and his dates, see my "On the Vicissitudes of Subhūticandra's *Kāma-dhenu* Commentary on the *Amarakośa* in Tibet," *Journal of the International Association of Tibetan Studies*, no. 5 (December 2009), 21 ff., ht (accessed December 17, 2011).

Bsam gtan bzang po, another disciple of Bcom ldan ral gri as well as his biographer, singles out two disciples of Bcom ldan ral gri in his biography of his master, namely, the madhyamaka scholar and logician (*dbu tshad pa*) Rin chen bzang po and Dbus pa Blo gsal Rtsod pa'i seng ge.^① The manuscript of the catalog of a/the Snar thang Tanjur that is available to me is also signed "Dbus pa Blo gsal Rtsod pa'i seng ge" as is his work on the philosophical systems (*grub mtha'*, *siddhānta*).^② His commentary on the *Rtags kyi 'jug pa* and his short tract on archaisms (*brda rnying*) and their updates (*brda gsar*) that Mimaki Katsumi studied some time ago are simply signed by "Dbus pa Blo gsal."^③ An examination of a recent publication of a volume of what are purported to be seven specimen of his writings show that the authorship of two of these are questionable. These are rather original studies of the *Abhisamayālamkāra*, the likes of which I have never seen before. The first is titled *Legs spyad* [read: *dpyad*] *nyi ma'i 'od zer mtshon cha'i rgyal po* and the second *Legs dpyad blo'i mun sel*.^④ The author's name of the work is badly smudged in the colophon, but he mentions such early thirteenth century authors as Gnyal zhig 'Jam pa'i rdo rje and his disciple Gtsang drug pa, whereas the author's name of the second is quite clearly given in its colophon as Nyi ma brtson 'grus. Aside from the reproduction of the late nineteenth century Sde dge print of Dbus pa Blo gsal's work on the philosophical systems, the four remaining texts include two manuscripts of his *Rtags kyi 'jug pa* commentary, one manuscript of his exegesis of the *Sum cu pa*, and one short piece on the names of the Buddha from the *Bhadrakalpāsūtra*. Again, these are all signed by "Dbus pa Blo gsal."

Dbus pa Blo gsal also figures among the many Tibetan scholars who attempted to

① See *Bcom ldan rigs pa'i ral gri'i rnam thar dad pa'i ljon shing*, *Collected Works* [of Bcom ldan rig ral], vol. Ka (I) (Lhasa: Khams sprul Bsod nams don grub, 2006), 80.

② A slightly incomplete manuscript of the catalog can now be downloaded from thrc.org at W2CZ7507; for some preliminary notes on this work, see my "The *Tshad ma'i byung tshul 'chad nyan gyi rgyun*: A Tibetan History of Indian Buddhist *Pramāṇavāda*," *Festschrift Klaus Bruhn*, ed. N. Balbir and J. K. Beutze (Reinbek: Dr. Inge Wezler Verlag für Orientalische Fachpublikationen, 1994), 388–92. For the second, see especially Mimaki Katsumi, *Blo gsal grub mtha'* (Kyoto: Zibun Kagaku Kenkyūso, 1982). We also learn from the colophon of his *grub mtha'* text that another important teacher of his was Mchims 'Jam pa'i dbyangs—he should not be confused, as is so often done, with Mchims Nam mkha' grags (1210–1285), his more famous contemporary and the seventh abbot of the Bka' gdams pa monastery of Snar thang—, who was the author of a very well known *Abhidharmakośa* commentary for which see, for example, the edition in *Madzod 'grel mngon pa'i rgyan* (Xining: Krung go'i bod kyi shes rig dpe skrun khang, 1989).

③ See his "Two Minor Works Ascribed to Dbus pa Blo gsal," *Tibetan Studies. Proceedings of the 5th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies Narita 1989*, vol. 2, ed. Sh. Ihara and Z. Yamaguchi (Narita: Naritassan Shinashoji, 1992), 591–8, and "Dbus pa blo gsal no 'Shin kyū goi shu' —kōteibon shokō" [The *Brda gsar rnying gi rnam par dbye ba* of Dbus pa Blo gsal—a First Attempt at a Critical Edition], *Asian Languages and General Linguistics. Festschrift for Professor Tatsuo Nishida on the Occasion of His 60th Birthday* (Tokyo, ? publ., 1990), 17–54. For similar texts with different titles that are equally ascribed to Dbus pa Blo gsal, see my "Some Remarks on the Meaning and Use of the Tibetan Word *bam po*," *Zangxue xuekan* 5 (2009), 128, note 2.

④ See, respectively, the *Bka' gdams gzung 'bum phyogs bsgrigs*, vol. 89, ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Chengdu: Si khron dpe skrun tshogs pa / Si khron mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2009), 263–398, and 399–442.

calculate the year in which the historical Buddha's nirvana, that is, death, had taken place. In this connection, Seyfort Ruegg suggested that he had calculated the date of the Buddha's birth and nirvana in 1280, an iron-dragon year, on the basis of statements to this effect by Lha dbang blo gros (16th c.) and especially Smin grol gling Lo tsā ba Chos dpal (1654—1718), alias Dharmashrī.^① This has of course definite implications for the dates of his floruit. For if he had carried out this determination in 1280, then he was most probably born before 1260. Neither Tibetan scholar is always accurate in his chronological judgment, so that we cannot a priori accept this year as a hard fact. Seyfort Ruegg arrived at the year 1280, because Smin grol gling Lo tsā ba had said that four hundred and one years had elapsed from that year to "the iron-hen year of the present [sexagenary cycle]," that is, sometime between mid-February of 1681 and the beginning of January of 1682. He says this much in his retrospective autocommentary on the verse-text of his treatise on *Kālacakra* calendrical astronomy.^② The verse-text, which he had begun writing in the same iron-hen year and only completed much later in 1713, merely has it that, according to Dbus pa Blo gsal's calculation, three thousand eight hundred and forty-six years would have elapsed [in the iron-hen year] since the Buddha's nirvana. Here we should be aware that the learned Lo tsā ba was directly indebted to the introductory portion of Grwa phug pa Lhun grub rgya mtsho'i dpal's 1447 study of calendrical astronomy. In fact, as we learn from the printer's colophon (*par byang*) of Grwa phug pa's work, the printing blocks had been prepared as late as 1681 through the efforts of Dalai Lama V Ngag dbang blo bzang rgya mtsho (1617—82).^③ In that year, the Dalai Lama had written *par byang*-s for the freshly carved printing blocks of the general study of the *Kālacakra* Stag tshang Lo tsā ba Shes rab rin chen (1405—77) completed in 1467, for a commentary on the *Phyi rgyud* chapter of the *Rgyud bzhi* by Dar mo Sman rams pa Blo bzang chos grags

① *Rtsis kyi man ngag nyin byed 'sang ba'i rnam 'grel gser gyi shing rta*, *Collected Works*, vol. IV (Dehra Dun: Mindrolling Monastery, ? 1999), 57a-b [= ed. *Bod nams phun tshogs* (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1983), 75].

② See above n. 22.

③ See *Ngag dbang blo bzang rgya mtsho'i rnam thar*, vol. 3 (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1991), 440 [= *Collected Works*, ed. *Ser gtsug nang bstan dpe rnying 'tshol badu phyogs sgrig khang*, vol. 7 (Beijing: Krung go'i bod rig pa dpe skrun khang, 2009), 328].

(1638—after 1697),^① and for Padma 'phrin las' (1640—1718) early 1681 biographical study of exponents of the 'Dus pa mdo — Mdo dgongs pa 'dus pa teachings,^② etc. Regardless of whether or not the Lo tsā ba had access to this print or a manuscript of Grwa phug pa's treatise, his own work is obviously quite substantially indebted to it. In any event, Grwa phug pa noted that, while residing "in the seminary (*chos grwa*) of Bcom ldan ral gri," Dbus pa Blo gsal had determined that, in the iron-dragon year, three thousand four hundred and sixteen years had elapsed since the Buddha's nirvana. No indication is given of which sexagenary cycle this iron-dragon year may have been a part, but Grwa phug pa writes that Dbus pa Blo gsal's calculation took place one hundred and sixty-seven years before the year in which he was writing his own work. This means that, according to him, the iron-dragon year could only be the year that fell roughly in 1280 or, to be more exact by using the *Tabellen* in D. Schuh's seminal work on the Tibetan calendars,^③ the time period of February 3, 1280, to January 21, 1281. In addition, according to him, Dbus pa Blo gsal dated the nirvana to the awkward year of *circa* 2137 B. C. E.

In his study of the Tibetan calendars, *Rtsis la 'khrul pa sel ba, Elimination of Errors in Computation*, of 1442 — 3, 'Gos Lo tsā ba Gzhon nu dpal (1392 — 1481) addressed various earlier calculations of the Buddha's nirvana in considerable detail. In dealing with the Bka' gdams pa tradition [s.], he points out that Mchims Nam mkha' grags and others were authors of a calculation that located the nirvana in the wood-male-monkey year, that is, in the equally awkward year of *circa* 2137 BCE, and that they had

① The commentary in question cannot have been his interlinear commentary (*mchan 'grel*) on the *Phyi rgyud*, the *Bdud rtsi snying po yan lag brgyud pa gsang ba man ngag gi rgyud las dum bu bzhi pa phyi ma'i rgyud kyi mchan 'grel bka' phreng mun sel sgron me*, ed. Mtsho sngon zhang chen bod kyi gso rig zhib 'jug khang, Arura vol. 31 (Beijing: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2005), 145—644, since he completed it in 1690. Dalai Lama V affixes the phrase *dar khan thing gir e chen o tho che khan* to "Dar mo Sman rams pa" — see the reference in n. 24. Of course, *dar mo* is the name of a place that is located in Lho kha and *man rams pa* is a title that would mean something like "expert physician." Uniquely occurring in this passage of the autobiography, *dar khan thing gir e chen o tho che khan* is a Mongol title, which he may have received from Gushri Qan's (d. 1655) son Dayan Qan or indeed from the Manchu court. It probably reflects *darqan tengker ejen otueji qan* — *ejen otueji qan* reflects Tibetan *rje sman bla* —, and the entire phrase would mean something like "enduring tax-exempted lord chief physician." True, *dar khan* frequently occurs in the autobiography and is associated with an official seal (*dar khan gyi tham ka*) or document (*dar khan gyi yi ge*); see, respectively, *Ngag dbang blo bzang rgya mtsho'i rnam thar*, vol. 2 (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1991), 157, 469 [= *Collected Works*, ed. Ser gtsug nang bstan dpe rnying 'tshol bsdu phyogs sgrig khang, vol. 6 (Beijing: Krung go'i bod rig pa dpe skrun khang, 2009), 115, 343].

② See the *'Dus pa mdo dbang gi bla ma brgyud pa'i rnam thar ngo mtshar dad pa'i phreng ba* (Leh, 1972), 1—425. The author completed this work in 1681, the very same year in which it was printed. In the printer's colophon on p. 425, Dalai Lama V signs himself as the Crazy Tantrist of Za hor (*za hor gyi sngags smyon*) Zil gnön behad pa rtsal, the latter being the name most probably Zur Thams cad mkhyen pa Chos dbyings rang gröl (1604—69) had given him upon his initiation into the 'Dus pa mdo mysteries.

③ See *Untersuchungen zur Geschichte der tibetischen Kalenderrechnung, Verzeichnis der Orientalischen Handschriften in Deutschland, Supplement Band 16* (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner Verlag, 1973), * 66 *.

proclaimed that this year had been the position of Jo bo rje, that is, Atiśa.^① We do not yet have access to an immediate source of Mchims' calculation, but the library holdings of 'Bras spungs monastery contain a thus far unpublished thirteen-folio manuscript of a pertinent work that is attributed to him, namely, the *Ston pa bzhugs pa dang bstan pa ji srid gnas pa'i rtsis*, roughly, *A Calculation of the Buddha's Life and How Long the Teaching will Endure*, in which we certainly can expect this calculation to be present.^② This relatively short work is not registered in the abbreviated list of his oeuvre; that his disciple and successor Skyo ston Smon lam tshul khriims (1219–99) included in his undated biography of this important thirteenth century savant. However, what is relevant for our purposes is that Skyo ston does register one treatise related to the *Kālacakra* and one to the non-Buddhist but Shaivite *Svarodayatantra*, a compendium of various types of astrology, which had issued from Mchims' fecund pen.^③

'Gos Lo tsā ba categorically states that the Jo bo chen po, "the great Lord," to whom it was originally attributed in the earlier literature was *not* Atiśa—a common designation of him is indeed *jo bo* [*chen po'i*] *rje*—, but rather a certain Jo bo chen po Tshul khriims of Stod lung. And he writes that the attribution of this chronology to Atiśa "appears to have been mistaken in the referent of the mere phrase *jo bo chen po*" (*jo bo chen po zhes bya ba'i sgra tsam la 'khrul par snang ngo //*).^④ Commenting on the relevant passage of 'Gos Lo tsā ba's work, Grwa phug pa writes that, leaving aside the issue of whether or not the person in question was Atiśa, it can be gleaned from what the young Bka' gdams pa scholar Dbus pa Blo gsal had written that it was not he who had inadvertently made such an error.^⑤ In all fairness, 'Gos Lo tsā ba does not mention Dbus pa Blo gsal in this context or, for that matter, anywhere else in his *Rtsis la 'khrul pa sel ba*. It is therefore possible to assume that he was not privy to a manuscript of the text in which Dbus pa Blo

① *Rtsis la 'khrul pa sel ba* [1466 ? Rtsed/Rtses thang/Sne'u gdong print], 14b–5a. The opening phrase is, 'chims nam mkha' grags la sogs pa kha cig gi bzhed pas ni /.

② 'Bras spungs dgon du bzhugs su gsol ba'i dpe rnying dkar chag, Snad cha [2], ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Beijing, Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2004), 1677, no. 019093.

③ *Mchims nam mkha' grags kyi rnam thar*, *dbu can* text in 50 folios, Cultural Palace of Nationalities, catalog no. 002806 (13), 38a–b; on fol. 16b, we read that he learned *Kālacakra*—based computational astronomy from a Gdong lung pa Nam mkha' rdo rje. This tallies with Mchims' record of teachings received, for which see *Mkhan po phyims* [read, *mchims*] *pa'i gzan yig*, *Bka' gdams gsung 'bum phyogs bsgrigs*, vol. 61, ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Chengdu, Si khron dpe skrun tshogs pa/Si khron mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2009), 46; part of his name is here spelled Sdong lung pa. The authorship of *Mkhan po chen po rnam par thar pa'i gzan yig* in *Bka' gdams gsung 'bum phyogs bsgrigs*, vol. 61, ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Chengdu, Si khron dpe skrun tshogs pa / Si khron mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2009), 7–34, was wrongly identified. This work is not Mchims', but Skyo ston's *gsan yig*. Further, on the final page there is a note to the effect that this manuscript had apparently at one time belonged to a certain Rtsed pa Bsod nams blo gros.

④ *Rtsis la 'khrul pa sel ba*, 20b.

⑤ *Dpal dus kyi 'khor lo las 'byung ba'i rtsis kyi tshul la yang dag pa'i ngag sbyin pa legs par bshad pa padma dkar po'i zhal lung* [Dgo' lden phun tshogs gling xylograph, 1681], 5b–6a [= *Rtsis gzhung pad dkar zhal lung*, ed. Yum pa (Beijing, Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2002), 7].

gsal had drawn up these calculations, so that he cannot be blamed for having misread him, if that were indeed Grwa phug pa's intention. In any event, Grwa phug pa reproduces Dbus pa Blo gsal's narrative of a series of calculations that had been carried out in Tibet by taking the Buddha's passing as his point of departure.^① Albeit with some important changes and omissions, this narrative was also paraphrased by Lo tsā ba Chos dpal.^②

Now this very same narrative is also reproduced in the work under discussion, albeit with one important caveat. Here the narrative is substantially more complete in that it begins with a portion that is absent from Grwa phug pa's quotation. The narrative in its entirety has a number of arithmetic problems and I am sure that I have not been able to solve all of them. This also holds for the episodes to which it refers, some of which remain unidentified. It begins as follows:

'dir ston pa 'das nas lo brgya bdun bcu rtsa lnga na rgyal po dga' byed byon /
de nas lo brgyad brgya na rgyal po zla srung dang / de nas lo nyis brgya sum
bcu rtsa 1 na rgyal po mdzod mangs dang / de nas lo bdun brgya nyi shu rtsa 4
na bal yul du rgyal po chos kyi go cha dang / de nas lo brgyad brgya 14 na bal
po rgyal po 'o'o re [read: 'od zer] go cha byon te / de rnams kyi lo tshigs bcos
so // de nas chu pho stag [g]i lo btsan po khri gtsug gis (gloss: brgyad bcu
drug bsnan nas) brtsis te / lo nyis stong brgyad brgya sum bcu rtsa brgyad'das
so //

In this connection, King Dga' byed [* Rāma] appeared one hundred and seventy-five years after the Teacher's passing. Eight hundred years hence, King Zla srung [* Candragupta] appeared, two hundred and thirty-one years hence, King Mdzod mangs [* ?], seven hundred and twenty-four years hence, King Chos kyi go cha [* Dharmavarma] in Nepal, eight hundred and fourteen years hence, the Nepalese King'Od zer go cha [* Arṣuvarma]; these adjusted the reign years (*lo tshigs*). Then, in the water-male-tiger year, Mighty One (*btsan po*) Khri gtsug (gloss: after adding eighty-six years) did a calculation; two thousand eight hundred and thirty-eight years have expired since the Buddha's passing.

The question is who is Khri gtsug? There is *prima facie* but one possibility, namely, that he was Khri gtsug lde btsan (806–41), alias Ral pa can.^③ This means that the water-

① *Dpal dus kyi 'khor lo las 'byung ba'i rtsis kyi tshul la yang dag pa'i ngag sbyin pa legs par bshad pa padma dkar po'i zhal lung*, 4b–5b [= *Rtsis gzhung pad dkar zhal lung*, ed. Yum pa, 5–6]. This seminary was most certainly located in Snar thang.

② See above n. 22.

③ See P. K. Sørensen, *Tibetan Buddhist Historiography. The Mirror Illuminating the Royal Genealogies*, Asiatische Forschungen, Bd. 128 (Wiesbaden, Harrassowitz Verlag, 1994), 419–427.

male-tiger year must reflect 822 AD, the year in which the well-known Sino-Tibetan peace treaty was concluded. The basic data for this ruler that are given by our anonymous author is that he was born in Brag dmar, in a dog-year (806), that he assumed rule in a wood-year at the age of "21" [read: "12"] (817), and that he passed away in Lhan dkar, in a hen-year (841) [p. 278–9]. If the water-male-tiger year indeed refers to the year 822, then the Buddha's nirvana should be calculated to have fallen in *circa* 2016–7 BCE! On the other hand, were Khri gtsug an abbreviation of Khri lde gtsug btsan, alias Mes 'ag tshoms, the father of Khri srong lde btsan, then the year 726 comes in question, regardless of the two sets of dates that the sources give for him, 680 to 742 or 704 to 742. ① But this would mean that the Buddha's nirvana fell in *circa* 2112 BCE! The two calculations in the text that follow the mention of Khri gtsug are the wood-female-sheep year (? 815) in which members of the Tibetan royal family had done a calculation on an unspecified occasion, and the water-female-hen year (853 [sic!]) in which Khri gtsug lde btsan allegedly passed away. The usual year that Tibetan sources give for his passing is not the water-female-hen but the dozen-year earlier iron–sheep year, that is, 841. It often happens that discrepancies of one or more units of twelve-years come into play when, as is so commonly done in the later literature, the twelve-year duodenary is converted into the sixty-year sexagenary cycle. There is no question that the year 853 instead of 841 was the result of such a miscalculation.

From the narrative that follows we know that in our author's opinion Dbus pa Blo gsal was of the view that the Buddha's nirvana had taken place in *circa* 2137 BCE. This presents us with a problem, not to mention the notice of the gloss. Aside from an arithmetic difference, portions of this narrative have precedents in the works of Slob dpon Bsod nams rtse mo's and Sa skya Paṇḍita to which I alluded to above, namely, the sections on *bstan rtsis*—chronology in the former's introduction to Buddhism, the *Chos la 'jug pa'i sgo*, of 1167/8, and in the biography of the Slob dpon's younger brother Rje btsun Grags pa rgyal mtshan that was written by their nephew Sa skya Paṇḍita in 1216. ② Their work begins with a quotation from the elusive *Lugs chen po* about the Indian kings' reign-years, which, even if is presented within a very flimsy context, also seems to be the direct or indirect source for the above passage of our anonymous author; the quotation reads:

'di yi gтам ni lugs chen po zhes bya ba las //
g. yul brtan 'og tu nyis stong lon //

① Sørensen, *Tibetan Buddhist Historiography. The Mirror Illuminating the Royal Genealogies*, 350–8.

② The references to these two works that follow are respectively based on Sa skya gong ma rnam lnga'i gsung 'bum dpe bsdur ma las bsod nams rtse mo'i gsung pod gsum pa, *Mes po'i shul bzhag* 8, ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Beijing, Krung go'i bod rig pa dpe skrun khang, 2007), 492–3, and Sa skya gong ma rnam lnga'i gsung 'bum dpe bsdur ma las sa paṅ kun dga' rgyal mtshan gyi gsung pod gsum pa, *Mes po'i shul bzhag* 18, ed. Dpal brtsegs bod yig dpe rnying zhib 'jug khang (Beijing, Krung go'i bod rig pa dpe skrun khang, 2007), 292–4.

dga' byed 'og tu brgyad brgya ste //
zla srung nyis brgya sum cu gcig //
[b]rjed mangs bdun brgya nyi shu bzhi //
bal gnas brgyad brgya [b]cu rtsa bzhi //
go cha nyis brgya bzhi bcu gnyis //
zhes'byung ste -/

An account of this [the reign years]: it is stated in the *Lugs chen po*:
 "After Yudhiṣṭhira, two thousand have gone by;
 After Rāma, eight hundred;
 [After] Candragupta, two hundred and thirty-one;
 [After] [B] Rjed mangs, seven hundred and twenty-four;
 [After] ? Bal gnas, eight hundred and forty-four;
 [After] Varma, two hundred and forty-two."

They then continue with an alternative narrative to which I intend to return in a planned study of the entire passage in both texts. With but several variants, the readings of all three texts more or less coincide with the notice that in the wording of Slob dpon Bsod nams rtse mo:

...bod kyi rgyal po khri gtsug lde btsan gyi sku ring la brtsis te / ... chu pho
stag lo 'di phan chad sangs rgyas mya ngan las 'das tshun chad spyir sdom na
lo nyis stong dgu brgya lnga bcu rtsa lnga lon te / slan chad kyang de bzhin du
brtsi'o //

...a calculation was done during the life time of the Tibetan king Khri gtsug lde btsan... if we summarize in general the years from this water-male-tiger year (822) to the Buddha's nirvana (ca. 2133 BCE), then two thousand nine hundred and fifty-five years have gone by; will be calculated thence accordingly.

The difference between this calculation of the Sa skya pa scholars and the one our anonymous author attributes to Dbus pa Blo gsal is therefore a hundred and seventeen years. Grwa phug pa summarizes the calculation of the latter before he actually cites from the work of Dbus pa Blo gsal:

ston pa'das nas lo nyis stong brgyad brgya sum cu rtsa brgyad 'das pa chu pho
stag gi lo la btsan po khri gtsug gis brtsis /

Two thousand and eight hundred and thirty-eight years had passed after the

Buddha's passing, in the year of the water-male-tiger (822), Mighty One Khri gtsug performed a calculation.

We will see that Grwa phug pa briefly addresses the arithmetic problem after he subjoined summary with a long quotation from Dbus pa Blo gsal's calculation. While the pagination of the passage that is reproduced below follows the block print and the edited text of Grwa phug pa, the text itself is taken from the quotation by our anonymous author and the more significant variants in Grwa phug pa's citation are noted along the way:

de nas shing mo lug gi lo la btsan po yab mched khu dbon gyis [5a] brtsis te lo nyi stong dgu brgya lnga bcu rtsa gcig 'das so // de nas chu mo bya'i lo rgyal po ral pa can 'das pa'i dus su brtsis te lo nyis stong dgu brgya brgyad cu rtsa dgu 'das so // de nas me mo glang gi lo slob dpon rong gong rin po ches brtsis te lo sum stong brgya rtsa 13 'das so // de nas sa mo glang gi lo stod kyis btsad po yab mched rnams dang zhang zhung seng ge 'dzom po'i dus su brtsis te lo 3 stong brgya nyi shu rtsa lnga 'das so // de nas me pho 'brug gi lo lha bla ma yab sras 3 rum yul du 'dzom pa'i dus su brtsis te lo 3 stong brgya lnga bcu rtsa 2 'das so // di bas lo 45 nyung bar brtsi ba ni mar yul du ban dhe chos kyis blo gros kyis brtsis pa man chad mi mthun pas dpyad do //^a de nas sa pho 'brug gi lo stod lung [s] su jo bo chen po tshul khrims kyis brtsis te lo 3 stong brgya 64 'das so // de nas lcags mo yos bu'i lo jo bo chen po rjes brtsis te lo sum stong brgya brgyad cu rtsa lnga^b 'das so // de nas me mo bya'i lo mnga' ris stod pa'i^c chos nyan rnams kyis ra dza^d 'dzims su brtsis te / lo 3 stong brgya dgu bcu rtsa 3 'das so // de nas sa mo glang^e gi lo lo tsā ba chen po blo ldan shes rab'das te phyi de stag gi lo 'du ba chen po byas pa'i dus su brtsis te lo 3 stong nyis brgya 46 'das so // de nas me mo bya'i lo zhang tshes spong ston pas^f ra sa 'phrul snang du brtsis te lo 3 stong nyis brgya 53 'das so // de nas chu mo phag gi lo nyang phran^g chos kyis ye shes kyis ngan lam yul du^h brtsis te lo sum stong 2 brgya 77ⁱ 'das so // de nas lcags pho [p. 317] 'brug gi lo^j phya pa chos kyis seng ges ngang 'gro'i gtsug lag khang du brtsis te [5b] lo sum stong nyis brgya 96 'das so // de nas shing pho 'brug gi lo dge ba'i bshes gnyen nam mkha' blo gros kyis brtsis te lo sum stong sum brgya nyi shu 'das so // de nas me mo sbrul gyi lo dpal ldan snar thang du mkhan po bstan pa'i rtsa lag chen pos dbu ma snang ba gsung ba'i dus su brtsis te lo sum stong sum brgya 93 'das so // de nas lcags pho 'brug gi lo la bcom ldan ral gri'i chos grwa chen por dbus pa blo gsal gyis brtsis te lo sum stong bzhi brgya dang 16 'das pa dang / stong dang brgyad bcu rtsa 4 gnas shing lnga brgya rtags tsam 'dzin pa yin no // deng sang ni chos dus dang 'dzam bu gling pa rnams kyis tshe tshad 60 pa yin la / tshe tshod lnga bcu'i dus na dam pa'i chos nub par 'gyur bar bshad do //^k

^a The entire sentence is absent.

^b *bdun*, "seven."

^c *kyi*.

^d *sa*.

^e Gloss: *me mo phag zer*, "fire-female-pig (1107) is alleged."

f *chos kyi bla mas for ston pas*, "by Chos kyi bla ma."

^g *bran pa*.

^h *ngan lam yul du* is absent.

ⁱ *bdun cu rtsa dgu*, "seventy-nine."

^j ...*lo la dang 'gro'i gtsug lag khang du* ...

Then, in the wood-female-sheep year (? 815), the Mighty One, the father, brothers, uncles and nephews made a calculation; 2951 years had passed. Then, in the water-female-hen year (853 [sic!]), a calculation was made on the occasion of emperor Ral pa can's passing^①; 2989 years had passed. Then, in the fire-female-ox year (977), Master Rong gong Rin po che made a calculation; 3113 years had passed. Then, in the earth-female-ox year (989), a calculation was made on the occasion of a treaty between Mighty One of Stod, the father [? of Lha bla ma] and his brothers,^② and Zhang zhung Seng ge; 3125 years had passed. Then, in the fire-male-dragon year (1016), Lha bla ma, the father and

① It is the general consensus that this emperor died in 841, that is one twelve-year, duodenary cycle earlier; see Sørensen, *Tibetan Buddhist Historiography. The Mirror Illuminating the Royal Genealogies*, 426, n. 1501.

② This seems to refer to Bkra shis mgon and his elder and younger brothers Pal byin mgon and Leg gtsug mgon, according to the orthography in J. Hackin, *Formulaire Sanscrit-Tibétain du Xe Siècle* (Paris: Librairie P. Guenther, 1924), 18; the *Formulaire* was recently revisited in M. Kapstein, "New Light on an Old Friend: PT 849 Reconsidered," *Tibetan Buddhist Literature and Praxis, Studies in its Formative Period, 900–1400*, ed. R. M. Davidson and Chr. K. Wedemeyer (Leiden: Brill, 2006), 9–30. Other sources such as the early thirteenth century religious chronicle by Lde'u Jo sras and the religious chronicle of Mkhas pa Lde'u have respectively Dpal gyi mgon and Lde gtsug mgon, and Dpal mgon and Gtsug lde mgon; see the *Lde'u chos 'byung*, ed. Chos 'joms (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1987), 146, and the *Mkhas pa lde'u mdzad pa'i rgya bod kyi chos 'byung*, 380. Both Lde'u Jo sras and Mkhas pa Lde'u belonged to the Old (*nying ma*) school.

two sons, made a calculation at the time of their meeting in Rum country^①; 3152 years had passed. The calculation of 45 years less than this should be investigated, since it is not consistent with what Ban dte Chos kyi blo gros in Mar country had calculated onward.^② Then, in the earth-male-dragon year (1028), Jo bo chen po Tshul khriims made a calculation in Stod lung; 3164 years had passed.^③ Then, in the iron-female-hare year (1051), Jo bo chen po Rje made a calculation; 3185 years had passed. Then, in the fire-female-hen year (1057), Mnga' ris Stod students of dharma made a calculation in Ra sa 'Dzims;^④ 3193

① Lha bla ma refers of course to Lha bla ma Ye shes 'od (947–1019/24) and his sons Khri lde mgon btsan (? – 1023), alias De ba ra dza, and Lha 'khor btsan (988–1026), alias Na ga ra dza. For them, their dates, and the significance of the year 1016 in which Lha 'khor btsan was ordained and named Na ga ra dza, see the detailed remarks in R. Vitali, *The Kingdoms of Gu ge Pu hrang According to the Mnga' ris rgyal rabs by Gu ge mkhan chen Ngag dbang grags pa* (Dharamsala: Tho ling gtsug lag khang lo gcig stong 'khor ba'i rjes dran mdzad sgo'i go agrig tshogs chung, 1996), 183, n. 257, 241–2. Not available to Vitali was Gu ge Paṅ chen Grags pa rgyal mtshan's (1435–86) 1480 biography of Lha bla ma which adds some interesting details and differs in some places from what he was able to ascertain from his sources; see the *Lha bla ma ye shes 'od kyi rnam [s] thar*, 6a, 24a–b. This work was written at Lha bla ma's see of Mtho gling. My thanks go out to Mr. Gu ge Tsho ring rgyal for sharing with me his copy of this valuable *dbu med* manuscript in 41 folios. There, the elder son is called Lha lde mgon btsan and we learn that, in 996, he was ordained a monk by Paṅdita Dharmaphala and Lo tsā ba Rin chen bzang po (959–1055), and that he was killed (*grongs*) by an unspecified agent in 1027. Lha 'khor btsan, on the other hand, received his layman's vows in 998 at which time he was given the name in religion of Na ga ra dza. When his older brother was murdered a full eleven years (*lo ngo bo bcu gcig*) after his ordination in 1016, "he guarded for a full four years (*lo ngo 4*) the Teaching." We are now in 1031. The text then states: *nga lnga pa la ri'i gnas su zhi bar gshegs so //*, that is, perhaps, "in his fifty-fifth [year, 1032] he peacefully passed away (*zhi bar gshegs*) in Ri'i gnas." In 1488, Gu ge Paṅ chen's disciple 'Jam dbyangs Nam mkha' bstan pa wrote a brief study of his master's life, for which see the *Rnam thar dgos 'dod 'byung ba*, *dbu med* manuscript in 19 folios, Cultural Palace of Nationalities, catalog no. 002813 (4). The manuscript contains a post-colophonic note: *lcags thang pas sar ma'i 'du byed //*, which means: "a fingerprint by Lcags thang pa [= ? Lcags thang Rab byams pa Byams pa bsod nams (1474–1540)]." That is to say, Lcags thang pa was the owner of the original manuscript. Lastly, for Rum country, see Vitali, *The Kingdoms of Gu ge Pu hrang According to the Mnga' ris rgyal rabs by Gu ge mkhan chen Ngag dbang grags pa*, 252 ff.

② Lo tsā ba Chos dpel wrongly identified him as [Spyan snga] Tshul khriims 'bar whose dates are 1033 or 1038 to 1093 or 1103; see Hong rmin zhin [Huang Mingxin] and Zhe Hru'u cing [Xie Shuqing], *Bstan rtsis ka phreng lag deb* (Beijing: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2000), 319.

③ A very similar entry is already found in Slob dpon Bsod nams rtse mo, 1167/8 study of the Buddha's life and Buddhism, for which see note 37; the text has the reading: ... *stod kyi chos nyan pa'i ras 'dzims su brtsis pas* ... Dated the same time, the xylograph of its cognate passage in Sa skya Paṅdita's biography of Rje btsun Grags pa rgyal mtshan, for which see note 37, has on the other hand: ... *stod kyi chos nyan pa'i sar 'dzom dus su brtsis pa na / ...* Inserting *dus* between Bsod nams rtse mo's 'dzims and *su*, Vitali, *The Kingdoms of Gu ge Pu hrang According to the Mnga' ris rgyal rabs by Gu ge mkhan chen Ngag dbang grags pa*, 296, n. 456, translated the phrase as "... cotton clad practitioners were listening to sTod kyi Chos. As for the calculation. . . ." This passage is also quoted in the *Rtsis la 'khrul pa sel ba*, 13b; ... *stod kyi chos nyan pas / ra sa 'dzims su rtsis pa na* ... , and *Dpal dus kyi 'khor lo las 'byung ba'i rtsis kyi tshul la yang dag pa'i ngag sbyin pa legs par bshad pa padma dkar po'i zhal lung*, 7b [= *Rtsis gzhung pad dkar zhal lung*, ed. Yum pa, 9], confirms this same reading; it differs only in that it [correctly] has *brtsis pa na* and includes the gloss "Was it the fire-hen year?" (*me bya yin nam myam*). I take the reading of Sa skya Paṅdita's text to be a *lectio facillior*, and understand *su of ra sa 'dzims su* as a locative, whereby *ra sa 'dzims* is a place-name, 'dzims being a locale associated with Ra sa, that is, Lhasa. This passage, by the way, is omitted from Lo tsā ba Chos dpel's text.

years had passed. Then, Lo tsā ba Blo ldan shes rab died in the earth-female-ox year (1109);^① a calculation was made on the occasion of having convened a large gathering in the tiger-year (1110) subsequent to it; 3246 years had passed. Then, in the fire-female-hen year (1117), Zhang Tshes spong Chos kyi bla ma made a calculation at the Ra sa 'Phrul snang temple; 3253 years had passed. Then, in the water-female-pig year (1143), Nyang phran pa Chos kyi ye shes made a calculation; 3277 years had passed. Then, in the iron-male-dragon year (1160), Phya pa Chos kyi seng ge made a calculation in the Ngang 'gro monastery; 3296 years had passed. Then, in the wood-male-dragon year (1184), spiritual friend Nam mkha' blo gros made a calculation; 3320 years had passed. Then, in the fire-female-snake year (1257), the Abbot, the great assistant to the Teaching,^② made a calculation at lustrous Snar thang on the occasion of teaching [Kamalaśīla's] *Madhyamakāloka*; 3393 years had passed. Then, in the iron-male-dragon year (1280), Dbus pa Blo gsal made a calculation in the great seminary of Bcom ldan ral gri; 3416 years had passed, and the Teaching will remain for 1084 years and [in the last] five hundred years the Teaching has but the outside markings.^③ Nowadays, the dharma-time (?) and the life span of an inhabitant of the Jambudvīpa-world is sixty, but it is said that when the lifespan is fifty, the holy teaching will set.

To be sure, there is much in Dbus pa Blo gsal's narrative that is already foreshadowed or alluded to in the earlier Sa skya pa literature, but there are several important differences. Grwa phug pa is of course quite right when he points out that there is a significant problem in the chronology between the calculation of Khri gtsug and Ral pa can's death, and easily declares it to be inconsistent with authentic documents—a gloss states: “the text is contaminated or we must compare it with other manuscripts” (*yi ge ma dag gam dpe gzhan dang bstun dgos*). As was pointed out before, there is also no question that some of the other discrepancies in these narratives are due to having misread

① In a note that I had overlooked in my “On the Vicissitudes of Subhūticandra's *Kāma-dhenu* Commentary on the *Amarakośa* in Tibet,” n. 43, R. Krammer, *The Great Tibetan Translator. Life and Works of rNgog Blo ldan shes rab* (1059–1109) (München: Indus Verlag, 2007), 32–33, n. 6, already signaled at some length that there were problems with his dates. I hope to revisit the issues surrounding these in a future study.

② This must be a sobriquet of Mchims Nam mkha' grags. *Mkhas pa Lde'u mdzad pa'i rgya bod kyi chos 'byung*, 408–9, is our earliest witness of a notice in which a 'Chims [= Mchims] had said anent *Abhidharmakośa*, III: 99, that 3282 years had passed since AN, and that therefore 1718 years remained. The Mchims family was renowned for its expertise in and promotion of the *kośa*, but it is not yet known why this should have been. If Mchims and Mkhas pa Lde'u followed here the chronology attributed to Atiśa, then this Mchims did his calculation in circa 1146 and might therefore be identified as Nam mkha' grags' ancestor Mchims Brtson'grus bla ma.

③ For this epoch, see A. Macdonald, “Préambule à la lecture d'un *Rgya bod yig tshang*,” *Journal asiatique* CCLI (1963), 65, and P. K. Sørensen, *A Fourteenth Century Tibetan Historical Work: Rgyal rabs gsal ba'i me long* (Copenhagen: Akademisk Forlag, 1986), 48–9.

the numbers in the manuscripts as well as to having miscalculated the year when converting the twelve-year duodenary into the sixty-year sexagenary cycle. He is also right when he says that Dbus pa Blo gsal by and large follows the Sa skya pa school, but we may question his assertion that he had written things down according to what the abbot (*mkhan po*) had told him. The latter is presumably Mchims, for it is unlikely that "the abbot" refers to Dar ma rgyal mtshan, inasmuch as the known calculations attributed to him diverge remarkably from what we currently believe the Bka' gdams pa school's traditional opinion to have been.

In Tibet, the terminology associated with the Indo-Tibetan and/or the Sino-Tibetan calendars is used to designate each year of the sixty-year, sexagenary cycle of Jupiter. As is known, the Indo-Tibetan vocabulary is derived from the *Kālacakra* literature and, in particular, from the Vajrapāṇi's *Laghutantraṭīkā*, that is, the *Laghutantra-piṇḍ ārvhavarāṇa*^① – in Tibet, this work is often simply referred to as the *Stod 'grel, Commentary on the Uppermost Part [of the Laghucakrasaṃvaratantra]* –, where the names for each of these sixty years are given. The Sino-Tibetan designations are the oldest and we come across these in the earliest Tibetan writings.^② These undoubtedly derive from the substantial number of Chinese texts on astrology (*rgya rtsis*) that were translated into Tibetan during the imperial period, of which exemplars were recently recovered from the library holdings of the Potala. I have come across one lone mention of Dbus pa Blo gsal's name in the context of these vocabularies in Dpa' bo II Gtsug lag phreng ba's (1504–66) large 1536–40 study of Karma pa III Rang byung rdo rje's (1284–1339) *Rtsis kyi bstan bcos kun las btus pa*, his versified work on *Kālacakra* computational astronomy and the calendar that he completed in 1318. He notes that a handful of Tibetan intellectuals—he mentions Gos Lo tsā ba and a certain Smyal pa [= ? Gnyal pa] Lhamdzes—had equated the Indo-Tibetan *Kālacakra*'s *prabhava – rab byung* year with the Sino-Tibetan *shing pho byi ba*, wood-male-rat year, rather than with the much more common equivalent of the Sino-Tibetan *me mo yos*, the fire-female-hare year. According to the reckoning that underlies the latter, the Sino-Tibetan wood-male-rat year is usually made to correspond to the Sino-Tibetan wood-male-rat year. The latter is the equivalent of the Indo-Tibetan *raktākṣa* (Tib. *mig dmar*) year and occurs as year no. 58 in the sexagenary cycle and thus three years prior to the *prabhava – rab byung* year! Dpa' bo II

① For editions, see Newman, "The Epoch of the *Kālacakra Tantra*," *Indo-Iranian Journal* 41 (1998), 344–5, and C. Cicuzza, ed., *The Laghutantraṭīkā by Vajrapāṇi. A Critical Edition of the Sanskrit Text*, Serie Orientale Roma LXXXVI (Rome: Istituto Italiano per l'Africa e l'Oriente, 2001), 65. Cicuzza dates the *Laghutantraṭīkā* to "probably the end of the X century" (p. 13), and gives as reasons (pp. 24–5) that it is quoted in the *Vimalaprabhā* and that there is not any trace of its author's familiarity with the *Laghukālacakratāntra*.

② On this, see G. Uray, "The Earliest Evidence of the Use of the Chinese Sexagenary Cycle in Tibetan," *Tibetan and Buddhist Studies Commemorating the 200th Anniversary of the Birth of Alexander Csoma de Kőrös*, ed. L. Ligeti, vol. 2 (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1984), 341–60.

wonders where this might have had its origin and raises the following rhetorical questions^①:

*sngon dbus pa blo gsal sogs rgya nag dang yu gur gyi mkhas pa mang po las
chos nyan pa de dag gis ci'i phyir ngo ma zin / rgya nag snga ma'i lugs so zhe
na /'thad pa'i khungs ston zhig / rgya nag phyi ma'i lugs so zhe na rje de
bzhin gshegs pa sogs kyi dus rgya bodkyi'brul che zhing rgya nag gyi skad
byang ba'i bod kyi lo tsā ba ches mang na de dag gis ngos mi zin pa'i rgyu ci /*

Why did not those earlier ones such as Dbus pa Blo gsal etc. who had studied dharma with Chinese and Uyghur scholars^② notice this? If it is an early Chinese tradition, then show an adequate source! If it is a later Chinese tradition, then, the connection being great between Tibet and China during the time of Lord Karma pa V De bzhin gshegs pa (1384–1415) etc., why did those many Tibetan translators who had expertise in Chinese not notice this?

He thus invests Dbus pa Blo gsal with a measure of authority! The question must be asked where Dbus pa Blo gsal might have written his *bstan rtsis*—chronology. Both Brag dgon Zhabs drung Dkon mchog bstan pa rab rgyas (1801–66), in the introduction to his monumental history of Buddhism in Amdo of 1865, and A khu ching Shes rab rgya mtsho (1803–75), in his list of rare books, register that he had written a *chos 'byung*.^③ And this would indeed be the most likely source for his *bstan rtsis*. Reading through various Tibetan texts over the past thirty years or so, I am struck by the fact that I have only come across one single reference to the actual contents of “the *Chos 'byung* of Dbus pa Blo gsal.” The passage in question occurs in a query an anonymous person from Sog yal [read: yul], that is, Mongolia, posed to Rwa sgreng Khri chen Blo bzang ye shes bstan pa rab

① *Dpal dus kyi 'khor lo'i man ngag rtsis kyi bstan bcos kun las btus pa chen po'i rgyas 'grel rin po che'i gter mdzod* [print], 13b–4a, tbrc. org at W7503. According to the printer's colophon, the printing blocks for this work were carved during Dpa' bo II's lifetime with the financial support of Rdo rje sgrol ma, the “governor” (*dpon sa*) of Yar stod. The lettering was designed by Sprul sku Karma rgya mtsho, whereas the editor—cum—proofreader was Dge slong Choe rgyal bstan pa rab rgyas.

② An awareness of Tibetans having studied with Chinese and Uyghur scholars around the turn of the fourteenth century is a relative rarity in Tibetan literature. For a few notes on this, see my *The Kālacakra and the Patronage of Tibetan Buddhism by the Mongol Imperial Family*, The Central Eurasian Lectures 4, ed. F. Ventura (Bloomington: Department of Central Eurasian Studies, Indiana University, 2004), 55–7.

③ See, respectively, *Mdo smad chos 'byung*, ed. Senon lam rgya mtsho (Lanzhou, Gan su'u mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 1982), 7, and *Dpe rgyun dkon'ga' zhig gi tho yig don gnyer yid kyi kun +da bzhad pa'i zla 'od 'bum gyi snye ma*, Collected Works, vol. 7 (Lhasa Zhol xylograph, 1943), 415.

rgyas (1759—1815); the question that was asked of Rwa sgreng's abbot was^①:

*dbus pa blo gsal gyi chos 'byung na / sngon gyi rgyal po rnam gyi mtshan /
ding khri btsan pa sogs rgyal po mang po zhig gi mtshan yang / deng sang gi
bod skad du ci zer /*

What are the appellations of the early kings in the chronicle of Dbus pa Blo gsal and also the appellations of a good many kings such as Ding khri btsan pa^② etc. in contemporary Tibetan?

And the abbot is forthright but also a little parsimonious in his answer:

*bod kyi rgyal po rnam kyi mtshan / ding khri btsan po sogs de skabs chos ma
dar zhing / bon gyi 'dzin pa'i skabs la song gshis / bon gyi brda' yin 'dug pas
/ bod skad du 'grel rgyu med /*

As for the names of the Tibetan kings, *ding khri btsan po* etc. are of the period when Buddhism (*chos*) had not yet spread and thus belong to the period of Bon adherence. Since these are Bon terms, there is no reason to comment on them in terms of the Tibetan language [since these Bon terms are derived from the Zhang chung language].

Summa summarum: The text-internal information of our anonymous author suggests that he lived and wrote sometime in the beginning of the fourteenth century. The *terminus a quo* of his work is the *floruit* of Thar pa gling Lo tsā ba Nyi ma rgyal mtshan dpal bzang po, who may have passed away in *circa* 1330. As far as his religious affiliation is concerned, he was in all likelihood a Bka' gdams pa intellectual with strong ties to the Sa skya pa school. He had access to a decent library of older manuscripts that may have included various versions of the *Dbā' bzhed* and the *Lo rgyus chen mo*—*Great Annals* of the eleventh century Khu ston. Finally; his reverential mention of Dar ma rgyal mtshan, his *bstan rtsis*—chronology and the fact that Dbus pa Blo gsal is cited *in extenso* and is mentioned in the final page of his work, also suggests the existence of a close affiliation of the author with Snar thang monastery, even if he does not expressly cite Mchims Nam mkha' grags' calculations.

① For what follows, see *Sog yul sogs nas mdo sngags kyi gnad rnam la dri ba thung ngu byung rigs rnam kyi dri ba dang dri lan phyogs gcig tu bsdabs pa*, Collected Works, vol. 2 (Dharamsala: Library of Tibetan Works and Archives, 1985), 278—9.

② I have no idea who this might be.